

ETHICS IN SEARCH ENGINES – THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ETHICS MILL OF INTERNET SEARCH BASED ON A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Ethical discussions have now also gained importance in the digitalised world. The discourse often revolves around areas such as data protection, artificial intelligence or digital ethics in general. However, there is only few research on ethics in internet search so far, although search engines play a central role in access to information and knowledge today. 98% of all access to the internet is via search engines. Ethical problems in internet search are hardly discussed, and if they are, the dialogue is only sporadic or not conducted scientifically. What role ethics play in internet search is still little known.

The aim of this research project was to close this research gap to some extent. A systematic literature review was conducted to find out which ethical fields of action and norms in other areas of the digital world can be applied to internet search. The result is the Ethics Mill of Internet Search. The model summarises the identified fields of action, their interdependencies and meanings in the context of internet search.

ETHICS IN SEARCH – A NEGLECTED AREA IN THE SCIENTIFIC DISCUSSION

Search engines function as a kind of navigator. They show which data sets and information in the World Wide Web could match individual search queries. In a mediatised world full of complex digital structures and dependencies and an enormously confusing variety of data on the internet, they thus take on one of the most important roles for the dissemination of knowledge and information in today's societies [8, p. 19]. Search engine providers have been repeatedly criticised for years [1, p. 207]. As commercially active companies, they are accused of placing economic goals above the needs of users and of violating personal rights through the non-transparent collection of user data, among other purposes for personalised advertisements (micro targeting). It is also criticised that search results are not only individually adapted and changed for users, but also for commercial goals [8, pp. 20-21]. How the relevance of search results is determined is difficult to understand for users as well as for experts [1, pp. 207-208].

But if internet search is not exclusively about users, what other aspects are significant and what role do ethics play in internet search?

Internet search, like all technological innovations of mediatisation and digitalisation, is subject to many social processes and dependencies, including political, economic, technical or social developments. Internet search is

developing rapidly. At the same time, its interactions and effects on people and society are becoming increasingly difficult to calculate. Opaque political and social consequences can be the result [6]. A holistic ethical reflection is needed that takes into account all interdependencies and framework conditions as far as possible [4, p. 8].

Ethics in digital contexts have gained attention in recent years, especially with topics such as data protection and privacy, autonomous driving or, at the latest since the 2016 US elections, with the heated fake news debates [2, p. xiii]. However, the topic of internet search has been little explored in this context.

In order to close this research gap to some extent, this paper examines, on the basis of a systematic literature analysis, which fields of action and norms from other areas of digital ethics are transferable to internet search.

METHODOLOGY

The research approach was based on the scientific procedure shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Overview of the scientific approach

In order to gain insights for the research area "Ethics in Internet Search", a **systematic literature review (1)** was first conducted. This is mainly based on secondary literature, i.e. reports on primary or original science. These are empirical, theoretical, critical/analytical and methodological works from the subject areas of 'digital ethics' and 'digital search'. Possible relevant scientific publications were also integrated. The core of the research work consists of sifting through similar area ethics that are closely related to digitalisation and do not necessarily have a direct connection to digital search. The aim is to identify important ethical fields of action in digitalisation and to determine which questions they can raise in the context of internet search.

A concept-oriented literature analysis is carried out as a basis for the relevance argumentation of different fields of action of Internet search. This means that common concepts, subject areas and similarities, but also contrasts

within the literature are searched for in order to define suitable supercategories. The process is carried out with the help of a **concept matrix (2)** based on the guidance of Webster and Watson [10]. A total of 92 different sources were consulted (see Appendix A for an overview; the details of the individual sources have not been listed extra in this paper as this would lead too far; however, the sources can be requested from the authors if interested).

Instead of looking specifically for concepts, it makes more sense in this context to draw on the possible ethical fields of action and topics. In the concept matrix, the relevance of the individual topics in a publication was rated from a scale of 0-4. The rating reveals how intensively a work has dealt with the specific topic area:

- (4) = stood in the centre
- (3) = represented an important part
- (2) = was a part
- (1) = was briefly mentioned
- (0) = did not occur

During the concept-oriented implementation of the literature analysis two questions arise: Which aspects of the fields of action/topic areas are relevant for the Internet search? And on which argumentative basis can this be justified? For this purpose, the relevance for the internet search is determined according to several criteria:

1. **Universal argumentation:** an ethical topic can be universally argued for all area ethics equally/across the board and thus also applies to Internet search.
2. **Direct reference:** an ethical problem is already linked to Internet search in the literature of other area ethics.
3. **Indirect reference:** in the general literature on Internet search, topics are considered relevant which have also been prioritised in the literature of other area ethics, but without direct reference to Internet search.
4. **Comparison:** ethical problems arise from the contexts of other ethics, which are partly reflected in Internet Search in a similar or identical way.

If one of the four points mentioned applied, the importance for the internet search was additionally weighted according to how often the fields of action are addressed in the existing literature (quantity). Another criterion was how strongly the individual works focus on the respective field of action (quality) or to what extent a high level of importance can be implied from a correlation of different works of literature.

This **transfer process (3)** is to be understood as thesis development. Corresponding findings are therefore never described as facts, but as considerations or theses, or are addressed as open questions. The purpose of this procedure is to point out possible critical gaps in knowledge. On the one hand, the work provides a good overview of the topic and, on the other hand, highlights the discrepancy between what has already been addressed in the ethical context of internet search and what may still need to be reflected on ethically in the future.

Since ethics is a reflection of morals and values, it is important in the ethical consideration to also identify

concrete values. In a further process, it is therefore examined and presented from which central values the fields of action are/can be derived. This was done by creating a **value matrix (4)**. For this purpose, values and ‘value demonstrators’ (principles, rules or examples that always belong to a certain value and illustrate its meaning in a specific context, such as fields of action in this context) were collected in the literature analysis, which were recorded in connection with the individual topic areas. A complete overview of the values matrix and the related questions can be found in Appendix B.

All of this leads to the development of the Ethics Mill of Internet Search as part of the **presentation of results (5)**.

THE ETHICS MILL OF INTERNET SEARCH

As described under Methodology, different ethical fields of action were identified with varying degrees of importance for internet search, both universal and specific. In order to present their interdependencies and meanings in the context of internet search conclusively and clearly, the most important points were summarised in the concept of the *Ethics Mill of Internet Search*. Fig. 2 provides an overview.

Figure 2: The Ethics Mill of Internet Search

Within the framework of the methodological procedure, it was possible to work out that acting ethically always means orienting oneself to certain values negotiated within a society (e.g. human rights). Accordingly, this value orientation (indicated by A in Fig. 2) forms the core of the

ethics mill and must also be the focus for the internet search.

One challenge is that values differ greatly depending on culture and society (**cultural differences**). In an international context, dialogue must therefore take place again and again in order to reach agreement on common basic values despite different points of view. Internationally operating search engines, for example, have to consider to what extent adaptations of internet search to different legal situations are an interpretation of common values.

As a further aspect of value orientation, competences must be disseminated in a society that enable a public ethical dialogue. This means that **ethical literacy**, **technical literacy**, but also **specific data literacy** in the digital context are essential. It is not a question of all people having to acquire all competences equally. Rather, it is about answering the question: How detailed must different actors be trained in the three areas of competence so that they are able to make ethical decisions independently? These fields of action are thus the basis for an ethical orientation of internet search.

In order to ensure this ethical value orientation while taking cultural differences into account, the analysis further revealed that there are three subject areas that must always be considered and in every context of internet search (**see Rotor Blades of the Mill - B**). The first is that processes and systems of internet search **must be made comprehensible** so that they can be understood and ethically reflected upon. Standing up for an ethical value orientation also means **taking responsibility**. In order for processes to be ethically accompanied, it must therefore always be clearly defined who is responsible for what and to whom. And in a third step, it is also necessary to consider how certain processes, actors or even norms must or can be **reviewed and controlled**. This arises from the assumption that people do not always act according to commonly defined values, and ethical norms also need to be reviewed again and again. In this context, it is above all important not only to ask the question "whether, at all", but if so, "to what level of commitment". The level of commitment ranges from an open discursive review in the form of ethical reflection to control in the form of laws with sanctions and must be ethically justified in individual cases.

The issues of comprehensibility, responsibility and control/review generated from this have also recurred due to their generality in all fields of action of ethics in Internet search and have revealed specific challenges to these issues in the individual contexts.

The **millhouse (C)** represents the internet search itself. If one first follows the well-known presentation and argumentation of Meyer [5, p. 6], data are basically observable or measurable symbols (sensor data, metadata, a number, a word, etc.). Only when data are structured or interpreted in the form of symbols, information emerges (for example, a number becomes a date of birth and a sequence of letters becomes a name). Knowledge, on the other hand, only emerges when data is subjected to

statistical analysis in order to extract causal models, or circumstantial evidence is developed from it that can support differentiated decision-making.

Since the core of Internet search is the collection and dissemination of information and knowledge, the connections of digital knowledge creation just described can also be seen as fundamental for Internet search. Internet search can therefore be divided into four ethical areas of investigation [adapted from 7, p. 49]:

1. Ethics in data collection – crawling processes, collection of user data and other data collection activities by search engine providers, etc.
2. Ethics in information aggregation and knowledge creation – building of relevance of search results, further processing of user data, etc.
3. Ethics for accessing knowledge – way of presenting results, availability of search engine offers, etc.
4. Ethics of using knowledge – misuse of knowledge by search engine providers, etc.

These four areas of investigation form the processes within the mill (of internet search) that must be reflected upon ethically. Each ethical field of action in internet search must therefore always be derived from at least one of the four areas of investigation. However, each field of action must be examined for relevant ethical aspects not only in one, but in every process area of internet search (data collection, data transfer, access to knowledge, application of knowledge).

Since the mill maps the ethical contexts of internet search, it only runs with "search engine-specific" wind in the form of various ethical topic areas and **fields of action (D)**. These resulted – as described above – from the creation of the concept matrix (2) and the transfer process (3). In the illustration of the Ethics Mill of Internet Search in Fig. 2, the fields of action are described with guiding principles that could be taken from the Value Demonstrators of the Value Matrix (see also Appendix B). They provide a possible target orientation according to which various processes of Internet search should be aligned or reviewed:

- protect privacy,
- enable autonomous opinion-forming,
- ensure balanced distribution of power,
- master automation,
- respect intellectual property,
- minimise search engine biases,
- appropriate censorship,
- building ecologically, sustainable structures.

For this to work, the questions of responsibility, comprehensibility and control (**see rotor blades B**) must be answered in all fields of action. Therefore, the rotor blades fly over the different fields of action again and again in order to make applied ethics in internet search feasible. These are interdependent. Accordingly, the ethics mill can only run with all three rotor blades.

The field "Other ethical fields of action" points to the fact that there is no absolute completeness and correctness in ethics. In this respect, one could, for example, derive further basic principles from the contents of the core of the ethics mill:

- For value orientation: Worry about people
- For comprehensibility: Provide competencies
- For cultural differences: Enable international dialogue on values

Important questions were derived for the individual fields of action in the course of the analysis. Future scientific work or organisations can address these questions in their individual contexts. The list of questions can be found in Appendix C.

CONCLUSION

The aim of this research work was to provide an overview of ethical fields of action in internet search and the associated ethical questions. Answering these questions was not part of the analysis. Also, no ethical recommendations for action were developed and no specific requirements for the topic areas were determined. Rather, the aim was to offer approaches for further work that would deal ethically with the individual aspects of internet search.

The results of this work can be used in two ways.

(1) Scientific continuation:

The catalogue of questions offers many starting points for future scientific research on the ethics of internet search. It would be conceivable to develop answers and possible requirements for an ethical internet search. The fields of action identified could also be further developed. In cooperation with developers and search engine experts, processes (such as crawling, indexing, relevance of search results) could be reflected ethically in detail. Another approach would be to focus on individual process areas of internet search (data collection, data processing, access to knowledge, application of knowledge) or individual fields of action (e.g. according to the guiding principles) as an area of investigation.

(2) Ethical process guidance in internet search organisations:

The results can also be used for organisations in the internet search in order to accompany processes ethically in a holistic way. However, as an overview work that is not specifically designed for process accompaniment of organisations, it makes sense for this to additionally consult ethical guidelines that are specialised in ethical process accompaniment in organisations. These guidelines or frameworks are very universal and not specific to internet search. They thrive on the fact that contextual findings, such as the results of this analysis, can also be used to include as many important ethical aspects as possible in a specific context (here internet search). For example, the ethical data assistant (DEDA) [9] or the IEEE

7000 -2021 [3] could be used for this purpose. Especially the IEEE 7000-2021 standard, newly introduced on 15.09.2021 in the form of a framework, can support organisations or companies to accompany the development of systems from the beginning with ethical considerations and to anchor values in the system. It establishes a set of processes that organisations can incorporate at all stages of concept exploration and development. This standard supports management and engineering in communicating transparently with selected stakeholders to identify and prioritise ethical value

Independently of the approaches described, an ethics of internet search is also heavily dependent on the knowledge of commercial companies. In the future, ethical reflection on internet search will therefore also require cooperation with search engine providers. This can be achieved either top down through control and regulation or, in the authors' view, better through conviction and initiative on the part of the corporations themselves (by assuming independent responsibility).

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APPENDIX A

Concept matrix as result from the systematic literature analysis incl. all identified sources

The legend below shows which fields of action can be derived from the literature analysis and how intensively the individual publications have dealt with a field of action (scale from 0 to 4).

Context or area ethic	Source	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R
Algorithm ethics	Algo.Rules 2022	2	0	2	2	2	2	0	2	0	1	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0
Algorithm ethics	Algorithm Watch 2021	2	0	2	2	2	2	0	2	0	1	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	0
Algorithm ethics	Zweig 2019	1	0	1	1	2	2	0	2	1	1	0	0	0	4	2	0	0	0
Algorithm ethics	Serfas, Roth 2020	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0
Algorithm ethics	Wachsmuth 2022	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	2	3	4	0	0	0	0
Autonomous driving	Sträter 2019	0	0	2	3	2	3	0	4	0	0	1	0	0	3	0	0	0	0
Data protection and privacy	Wiesner 2021	2	0	0	2	2	1	0	2	0	2	4	2	2	1	0	0	0	0
Data protection and privacy	Aldenhoff et al. 2019	2	0	3	1	2	2	1	2	2	1	4	1	1	2	1	2	2	0
Data protection and privacy	Friedewald 2018	2	0	1	2	2	3	2	2	0	2	4	1	2	1	0	1	0	0
Data protection and privacy	Stapf et al. 2021	1	0	1	2	0	1	0	1	0	4	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Data protection /Data Ethics	Tranberg 2021	2	0	2	3	3	3	0	1	0	2	4	2	2	1	0	0	0	0
Data protection /Data Ethics	Eling 2018	2	0	1	0	1	2	0	2	0	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Data protection /Data Ethics	Hasselbalch, Tranberg 2018	2	0	0	0	2	2	0	2	1	3	4	0	0	2	0	0	0	0
Data protection /Data Ethics	Geuns, Brandusescu 2020	2	0	1	2	2	2	0	2	0	3	4	2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Digital Ethics	Perry 2017	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	0	2	1	0	0	0
Digital Ethics	Schäfer, Franzske 2020	2	1	2	2	2	1	0	1	0	0	2	2	2	2	0	2	0	0
Digital Ethics	Spiekermann 2019	3	1	1	3	2	2	0	2	1	3	2	2	0	2	0	0	2	0
Digital Ethics	Grimm 2020	2	1	2	2	2	2	0	2	3	2	3	1	2	2	0	0	2	0
Digital Ethics	Zöllner et al. 2015	2	1	1	2	4	3	0	2	2	4	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Digital Ethics	Schlegel 2020	2	1	0	1	2	2	0	1	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Digital Ethics	Achatz et al.2020	3	1	2	2	1	2	0	1	0	1	2	2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Digital Ethics	Baumann, Donskis 2013	4	1	2	2	2	2	0	2	1	2	2	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Digital Ethics	Weber, Mangold 2019	2	1	1	2	2	2	1	1	3	3	2	2	0	1	0	0	0	0
Digital Ethics	Ess 2020	2	3	1	2	2	2	0	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	0	0	0	0
Digital Ethics	Gogróf et al. 2017	2	1	2	2	2	1	0	2	2	0	2	2	0	1	0	0	0	0
Digital Ethics/Digital Transformation	Bridle 2018	3	0	3	1	2	2	0	2	3	2	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Digital Power Distribution	Volmar 2019	0	0	1	2	2	2	1	1	4	2	1	2	1	0	0	0	0	0
Digital Ethics of Law	Hoffmann-Riem 2018	2	0	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	3	2	2	1	0	1	0	0	0
Digital Transformation/Digital Change	Becker 2019	2	0	3	2	2	2	0	1	2	0	2	2	1	1	0	0	0	0
Digital Transformation/Digital Change	Kalina et al. 2018	2	0	2	1	1	2	0	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	0	2	0	0
Digital Transformation/Digital Change	Bedford-Strohm et al. 2019	2	0	2	2	2	2	0	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	0	0	0	1
Digital Transformation/Digital Change	Fend, Hofmann 2020	2	0	0	2	2	1	0	1	2	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	2	1
Digital Transformation/Digital Change	Hess 2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Digital Transformation/Digital Change	Radermacher 2018	0	0	2	2	0	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Digital Transformation/Digital Change	Mühlhoff et al. 2019	2	0	1	2	2	3	3	2	1	3	2	2	1	2	0	0	1	1
Digital Transformation/Digital Change	Jaekel 2017	2	0	1	2	1	1	0	1	0	4	1	1	0	2	1	0	0	0
Digital Transformation/Digital Change	Schnell, Dunger 2019	2	0	1	2	1	1	0	1	1	0	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	0
Digital Humanism	Fritz, Tomaschek 2020	2	0	3	2	2	2	0	2	1	3	2	2	1	2	2	0	0	0
Digital Humanism	Werthner et al. 2019	2	0	2	2	2	2	0	2	1	1	1	2	3	3	3	0	0	0
Digital Humanism	Nida-Rümelin, Weidenfeld 2018	2	0	2	3	3	2	0	2	1	1	0	0	2	4	3	0	0	0
Ethics in Graphics Design	Bauer et al. 2015	2	0	1	3	3	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ethics in Copyright	Amini 2017	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	4	0	0
Ethics in Internet Regulation	Küllmer 2019	2	0	1	1	1	2	3	0	2	3	1	1	0	1	0	3	0	0
Ethics in the IT	Spiekermann 2016	2	0	2	2	1	2	0	2	4	1	3	0	1	2	0	0	0	0
Ethics in the IT	Stapf et al. 2021	2	0	3	2	2	4	0	2	2	2	4	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
Ethics in Market Research	Keller et al. 2020	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	3	0	3	3	1	0	0	0
Basics in Ethics	Stoecker et al. 2011	2	1	2	2	1	2	0	2	1	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0
Basics in Ethics	Fenner 2019	2	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0
Basics in Ethics	Werner 2021	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	0
Basics in Ethics	Pieper 2017	2	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Social Theory	Nassehi 2019	0	0	0	2	2	2	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Social Theory	Bollmer 2018	2	3	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0
Social Theory	Zuboff 2018	2	0	0	2	2	2	0	2	1	2	1	2	0	1	0	0	0	0
Information ethics	Bendel 2019	2	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
Information ethics	Steinebach et al. 2020	2	0	2	2	2	2	1	2	4	2	1	1	2	2	0	0	0	0
Information ethics	Pariser 2011	0	0	2	1	2	0	2	1	4	1	1	1	1	3	0	0	0	0
Information ethics	Hohlfeld et al. 2020	1	0	2	2	2	2	1	2	4	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0

Context or area ethic	Source	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R
Internet Search	Unkel 2019	0	0	2	1	2	2	0	0	3	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
Internet Search	Lewandowski 2021	2	0	2	1	1	1	1	0	2	1	2	1	1	2	0	1	0	0
Internet Search	Giuseppe et al. 2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Internet Search	Burghardt et al. 2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Internet Search	IAB 2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Internet Search	Newton 2016	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Internet Search	Sens 2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Internet Search	Brückerhoff 2019	2	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	4	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
Internet Search	Amato et al. 2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Internet Search	Stark et al. 2014	2	0	2	2	3	1	2	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
Internet Search	Schulz 2015	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	2	0	2	1	1	0	2	0	0	0	0
Internet Search	Schrade 2021	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
AI-Ethics	Jobin et al. 2019	2	0	1	2	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1
AI-Ethics	Dilemmas in AI ² 2020	2	0	3	3	3	2	0	2	0	0	1	1	0	2	0	0	0	0
AI-Ethics	Serfas et al. 2015	2	0	1	2	1	3	0	0	2	1	2	2	0	4	0	0	0	0
AI-Ethics	Aoun 2017	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0
Machine Ethics	Grimm, Zöllner 2015	2	0	2	3	2	2	0	2	0	1	1	1	1	3	1	0	0	0
Machine Ethics	Capurro 2017	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Machine Ethics	Rath et al. 2019	2	0	1	3	3	2	0	2	0	1	2	2	3	4	2	0	0	0
Media Ethics	Schicha 2019	1	1	2	3	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	0	1	0	0	1	0
Media Ethics	Christians, Fackler 2020	2	1	1	2	2	1	0	1	2	1	2	2	1	1	0	0	0	0
Robot Ethics	Iben 2021	2	0	1	1	2	3	0	2	4	2	1	1	1	3	1	0	0	0
Social Media Ethics	Orlowski 2020	2	0	2	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	0	2	2	0	3	0
Social Media Ethics	Klimczak et al. 2020	2	0	3	2	1	1	1	0	3	0	1	1	2	2	1	1	0	0
Social Media Ethics	Kvalnes 2020	2	0	1	2	2	2	0	1	2	2	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
Social Media Ethics	McDonald 2016	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	3	2	2	2	0	0	0	2	0
Social Media Ethics	Niederer, Rogers 2020	2	0	1	2	2	2	0	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	0	0	0	0
Social Media Ethics	Tufekci 2017	0	0	3	1	2	1	0	1	3	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	0
Sociology of Technology	Häußling 2019	2	1	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sociology of Technology	Bridle 2018	0	0	3	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	2	0
Sociology of Technology	Kaminsky et al.2020	2	0	2	1	2	0	0	1	2	2	1	1	0	2	0	0	0	0
Business Ethics	Gadatsch et al. 2018	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Business Ethics	Achenbach et al. 2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Business Ethics	Nietsch-Hach 2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Business Ethics	Gogroß et al. 2017	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Business Ethics	Pietsch 2020	2	0	1	2	1	1	0	1	0	2	1	2	0	1	0	0	0	2
	Anzahl der Werte > 0 =	65	18	68	74	68	72	18	64	58	59	66	57	39	66	16	11	14	7

Legend:

- (A) Ethical value orientation:
Publications that fundamentally address the emergence and orientation of values in a digital world.
- (B) Cultural aspects:
Publications in which cultural differences in value concepts and international value discourses in digital ethics are addressed.
- (C) Public awareness/media literacy & education:
Publications addressing the role of education, the acquisition of certain skills and the importance of public awareness.
- (D) Responsibility:
Publications that address the acceptance or attribution of responsibility for ethical aspects.
- (E) Transparency and explicability:
Publications that deal with transparency or accountability in digital worlds.
- (F) Control:
Publications that ethically reflect on institutions of control and possibilities of control, including discourses on surveillance.
- (G) Censorship and information regulation:
Publications in which information regulation and censorship processes are ethically discussed.
- (H) Security and safe guarding:
Publications in which the security of human beings is thematised, on the one hand for the protection of life and on the other hand also for the protection of certain rights.
- (I) Knowledge creation and opinion formation:
Publications that deal with the creation of digital knowledge or the formation of opinion in digital environments.

- (J) Distribution and abuse of power:
Publications in which monopoly positions or unequal power relations are discussed.
- (K) Privacy and anonymity:
Publications that deal with privacy, anonymity and data protection.
- (L) Equality and Equal Opportunities:
Publications that deal fundamentally with criteria of fair interaction in digital worlds.
- (M) Prejudice and discrimination:
Publications that deal with discrimination and prejudices that arise through processes of digitalisation, including "racist" algorithms, cyber-bullying, social biases.
- (N) Automation and ethical algorithms:
Publications that deal with fundamental ethical problems and issues in the context of automation processes, including cooperation processes between humans and technology.
- (O) Humanisation of technology:
Publications that deal with ethical problems of the humanisation of technology, e.g. chatbots or AIs that are perceived as human.
- (P) Copyright and intellectual property rights:
Publications dealing with intellectual property in digital worlds.
- (Q) Addictions and addiction:
Publications dealing with addictions and addictive behaviour in digital worlds, e.g. internet addiction, mobile phone addiction, addiction mechanisms and commercial exploitation.
- (R) Ecological sustainability:
Publications that take an ecological perspective on digitalisation.

APPENDIX B

Value matrix incl. core values, values and value demonstrators

Autonomy	Empathy	Sustainability	Comprehensibility	Safe Guarding	Fairness	Privacy	CORE VALUES
Knowledge creation and opinion formation	Value orientation	Ecological sustainability	Transparency and traceability	Automation	Power / Power distribution	Data protection and privacy	Fields of action
Understanding	Responsibility			Control, verification and trust	Discrimination and prejudice		
				Censorship	Copyright		
					Cultural aspects		
Independency	Sympathy	Environmental awareness	Openness	Trust	Equality	Anonymity	VALUES
Freedom	Helpfulness		Clarity	Control	Tolerance	Intimacy	
Self-orientation	Responsibility			Protection	Respect	Protection	
Self-efficacy	Conscientiousness			Feasibility	Justice		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflective use and development of internet search • Be able to form a differentiated opinion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Caring for people • Protecting what is valuable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High energy consumption of data centres 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Paradox of complexity • Right to secrets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protect ethical values and norms • Master technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International discourse on values • Self-efficacy of the users • Heterogeneous distribution of power • Discriminatory AI • Right to beneficial ownership 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International self-determination 	VALUE DEMONSTRATORS

APPENDIX C

Questionnaire

A) General fields of actions – Core of the ethic mill of internet search – Value orientation

Value		Questionnaire
1) Value orientation and the ends-means dilemma	Guiding Principle: Worry about people	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How can actors (users, search engine providers, governments, etc.) who do not want to act ethically be persuaded to act in the interest of the common good? - How can internet search companies pursue a value strategy and still be profitable? - How can the tension between value strategy and cost pressure be resolved in a capitalist system? - How can it be ensured that internet search technologies are ethically considered from the outset?
	Core Value: Empathy	
2) Public awareness and understanding	Guiding Principle: Provide competences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What education is needed for the different stakeholders of internet search? - What support do people need to feel well informed to search the internet? - How detailed do different stakeholders need to be educated in the three fields of competence in order to be able to make ethical decisions autonomously?
	Core Value: Autonomy	
3) Cultural Differences	Guiding Principle: Enable international dialogue on values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How can ethical standards for internet search be defined in an international context? - What processes and actors are needed for the definition of international ethical standards in internet search?
	Core Value: Fairness	

B) The overarching importance of responsibility, explainability and control

Value		Questionnaire
1) Responsibility	Core Value: Empathy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In internet search, for what must responsibility be assumed by whom towards whom?
2) Transparency and comprehensibility	Core Value: Comprehensibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What must be made comprehensible to whom and in what form? - What must be made transparent to ensure traceability? - How can good documentation and logical structuring of internet search processes be ensured?
3) Ethical review, control and regulation	Core Value: Safe Guarding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What or who may/must be controlled or checked by whom for what reason and how bindingly? - Which processes/actors of Internet search must be controlled? - Who should be authorised to control Internet search processes and how and, in case of doubt, to regulate them? - How can processes of internet search be designed to enable an ethical exchange and to review applicable ethical norms again and again in the specific context?

C) Prioritised ethical fields of action for the internet search

Value		Questionnaire
1) Privacy and data protection	Guiding Principle: Protect privacy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How can it be ensured that personal data do not leave the informally protected framework?
	Core Value: Privacy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How can data protection regulations and laws be adapted to the current data processing methods of Internet search providers? - How can control and traceability over one's own data and its use be guaranteed? - To what extent can the algorithmic analysis of user data in internet searches be made comprehensible for the user? - How can the use of data for personalisation possibly be controlled by the user him/herself? - Does absolute control over one's own data also go hand in hand with absolute anonymity in the use of internet search? - What are the ethical grounds on which a state or an organisation can access personal data in internet search?
2) Knowledge creation and opinion formation	Guiding Principle: Enable autonomous opinion-forming	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How and for whom must processes/factors of digital knowledge creation (crawling, indexer, searcher, etc.) by search engine providers be made comprehensible?
	Core Value: Autonomy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What approaches are needed to prevent one-sided influence on opinions? - Should there be a possibility in future to switch off personalisation or to apply it only to certain search results? - Can personalisation also be ensured independently, e.g. by filter systems? - Should advertisements be part of the search result display, and if so, in what way? - What responsibility do search engines have in their role as mediators of disinformation? - Can the spread of misinformation through search engines be restricted?
3) Distribution and abuse of power	Guiding Principle: Ensure balanced distribution of power	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How can more diversity be ensured in the search engine market? - Which institutions can ethically control the distribution of power in internet search in the most unbiased way possible?
	Core Value: Autonomy/Fairness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How can data-related economies of scale be minimised in order to prevent monopolies? - For whom must power relations be made comprehensible? - How can end users be empowered in their use of internet search? - How can it be ensured that mechanisms of internet search are not abused by third parties? How transparent can internet search processes be for the public?
4) Automation and the fallibility of algorithms	Guiding Principle: Master automation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How can the field of unexpected conditions in Internet search automation processes be minimised?
	Core Value: Safe Guarding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Which Internet search processes should be automated and which should not? - To what extent can the traceability of automated processes in Internet search be guaranteed? - How can interfaces between different automation processes be controlled and transfer processes be traced? For example, what influence does the archiving of the search index have on the formation of relevance in the search results? - What do the automation processes of Internet search have to look like in order to be controllable? - If the processes of internet search cannot yet be made ethically comprehensible, must the function of internet search be restricted until this is possible?

Value		Questionnaire
5) Discrimination and prejudice	Guiding Principle: Minimize search engine biases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How can data selection procedures be influenced to minimise bias and technically generated discrimination? - How can search algorithms be optimised to avoid erroneous correlations? - To what extent do individualised search results actually systematically lead to disadvantages for different users? - What responsibility do search engine providers have to offer search results equally everywhere in the world?
	Core Value: Fairness	
6) Censorship and the exclusion of content by search engine operators	Guiding Principle: Appropriate censorship	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What data may be stored for censorship processes? - How can Internet searches be comprehensibly censored so that freedom of information or opinion are not restricted? - To what extent do search engine providers have to guarantee that third parties and control institutions have insight into their processes? - To what extent should censorship by search engines be dependent on the laws of individual countries?
	Core Value: Safe Guarding	
7) Knowledge Graph results and copyright	Guiding Principle: Respect intellectual property	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To what extent may search engines use third party content to make internet search more user-friendly? - How could third parties make their content available for a more efficient internet search without disadvantages for themselves?
	Core Value: Fairness	
8) Ecological sustainability	Guiding Principle: Building ecological, sustainable structures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How can environmentally sustainable data centres for internet search be ensured?
	Core Value: Sustainability	